

Energy and Flexibility Modelling

Hands-on 5 (macOS)

Please use the following citation for:

- **This exercise**

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- **clicSANDMac Software**

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- **OSeMOSYS Google Forum**

Please sign up to the help Google forum [here](#). If you are stuck, please ask questions here. If you get ahead, please answer questions in the same forum. Please state that you are using the 'clicSAND' Interface.

Learning outcomes

By the end of this exercise, you will be able to:

- (1) Define an existing thermal power plant taking in fuel to generate electricity
- (2) Define the existing transmission network
- (3) Define the existing distribution network
- (4) Run the model and check results on production by technology and capacity of each technology

Define an existing thermal power plant taking in fuel to generate electricity

In Lecture 6, we learnt how to represent a technology in OSeMOSYS and which parameters characterize thermal power plants and transmission and distribution technologies.

In this Hands-On, we will add 6 technologies in total: 4 thermal power plants, 1 technology representing the transmission system and 1 for the distribution network. Two new fuels will be added to the model: **ELC001** (Electricity coming directly from power plants) and **ELC002** (Electricity after transmission). We will build this part of the RES:

In order to represent a thermal power plant, remember that the following **parameters** must be considered:

- **InputActivityRatio**: defines the rate of fuel consumed (i.e. Coal)
- **OutputActivityRatio**: defines the fuel provided (i.e. Electricity)
- **CapacityToActivityUnit**: used to convert data related to the Capacity of technology into the Activity it can generate. For primary supply technology, this value should be set to 1.
- **Fixed Cost**: defines the fixed Operation & Maintenance cost (\$/kW)

- **CapitalCost**: defines the overnight investment cost of the plant (\$/kW)
- **OperationalLife**: defines the lifetime of the technology (in years)
- **ResidualCapacity**: defines the existing capacity of the technology (in GW) and its expected decommissioning.
- **Capacity Factors**: represents the variability in generation at each point in time.

Let's add **PWRCOA** - the technology representing a coal power plant.

1. Go to SETS and in cell B10 change the name from "TEC007" to "**PWRCOA**" and the description to "**Coal Power Plant**". In this way, we add the technology which will be transforming Coal (**COA**) into electricity (**ELC001**) to the model.
2. Now let's add the **Electricity from Power plants** in Cell E7 following the same procedure.
3. Next, go to Parameters Sheet and filter out in Column C for **PWRCOA** (as done previously).
4. Add the data for **PRWCOA** as for the tables below and as given in the [DataPrep file](#).
 - a. **InputActivityRatio**: choose the Coal Fuel row (Cell K21514) and add data from 2015 to 2070

1	Parameter	TECHNOLOGY	FUEL	variables	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
21513	InputActivityRatio	PWRCOA	ELC003		0	0	0	0	0	0
21514	InputActivityRatio	PWRCOA	COA		2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7
21515	InputActivityRatio	PWRCOA	OIL		0	0	0	0	0	0

b. **OutputActivityRatio**:

Parameter	TECHNOLOGY	FUEL	Time independent variables	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
31672	OutputActivityRatio	PWRCOA	ELC003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31673	OutputActivityRatio	PWRCOA	COA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31674	OutputActivityRatio	PWRCOA	OIL	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31675	OutputActivityRatio	PWRCOA	NGS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
31676	OutputActivityRatio	PWRCOA	ELC001	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
31677	OutputActivityRatio	PWRCOA	CDM006	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

- c. **CapacityToActivityUnit, CapitalCost and FixedCost** respectively in rows 19571, 19770, and 20971.

1	Parameter	TECHNOLOGY	FUEL	Time independent variables	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
19571	CapacityToActivityUnit	PWRCOA		31.536									
19770	CapitalCost	PWRCOA			1600	1600	1600	1600	1600	1600	1600	1600	1600
20971	FixedCost	PWRCOA			65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65	65
21513	InputActivityRatio	PWRCOA	ELC003		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
21514	InputActivityRatio	PWRCOA	COA		2.56	2.56	2.56	2.56	2.56	2.56	2.56	2.56	2.56

d. OperationalLife

21560	InputActivityRatio	PwRCOA	COM048		0	0
21561	InputActivityRatio	PwRCOA	COM049		0	0
21562	InputActivityRatio	PwRCOA	COM050		0	0
31130	OperationalLife	PwRCOA		35		
31672	OutputActivityRatio	PwRCOA	ELC003		0	0
31673	OutputActivityRatio	PwRCOA	COA		0	0
31674	OutputActivityRatio	PwRCOA	OIL		0	0
31675	OutputActivityRatio	PwRCOA	NGS		0	0
31676	OutputActivityRatio	PwRCOA	ELC001		1	1

- e. **Residual Capacity:** defines the existing capacity of the technology (in GW) and its expected decommissioning
- f. **Capacity Factors:** represents the variability in generation at each point in time. You need to define capacity factor values for all the modelling years from 2015 to 2070. Therefore, copy-paste the data available in the Data Prep file (**from J48 to J143**) for the year 2015. Then copy paste the **same values** for all the years until column BM correspondent to 2070.

1	Parameter	TECHNOLOGY	TIMESLICE	2015	2016	2070
69	AvailabilityFactor	PwRCOA		1	1	1
70	AvailabilityFactor	PwRCHC		1	1	1
71	AvailabilityFactor	PwRNGS001		1	1	1
72	AvailabilityFactor	PwRNGS002		1	1	1
73	AvailabilityFactor	PwRTRM		1	1	1
74	AvailabilityFactor	PwRDIST		1	1	1
333	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S101	0.85	0.85	0.85
334	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S102	0.85	0.85	0.85
335	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S103	0.85	0.85	0.85
336	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S104	0.85	0.85	0.85
337	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S105	0.85	0.85	0.85
338	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S106	0.85	0.85	0.85
339	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S107	0.85	0.85	0.85
340	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S108	0.85	0.85	0.85
341	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S109	0.85	0.85	0.85
342	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S110	0.85	0.85	0.85
343	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S111	0.85	0.85	0.85
344	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S112	0.85	0.85	0.85
345	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S113	0.85	0.85	0.85
346	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S114	0.85	0.85	0.85
347	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S115	0.85	0.85	0.85
348	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S116	0.85	0.85	0.85
349	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S117	0.85	0.85	0.85
350	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S118	0.85	0.85	0.85
351	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S119	0.85	0.85	0.85
352	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S120	0.85	0.85	0.85
353	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S121	0.85	0.85	0.85
354	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S122	0.85	0.85	0.85
355	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S123	0.85	0.85	0.85
356	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S124	0.85	0.85	0.85
357	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S201	0.85	0.85	0.85
358	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S202	0.85	0.85	0.85
359	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S203	0.85	0.85	0.85
360	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S204	0.85	0.85	0.85
361	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S205	0.85	0.85	0.85
362	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S206	0.85	0.85	0.85
363	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S207	0.85	0.85	0.85
364	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S208	0.85	0.85	0.85
365	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S209	0.85	0.85	0.85
366	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S210	0.85	0.85	0.85
367	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S211	0.85	0.85	0.85
368	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S212	0.85	0.85	0.85
369	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S213	0.85	0.85	0.85
370	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S214	0.85	0.85	0.85
371	CapacityFactor	PwRCOA	S215	0.85	0.85	0.85

For **PWRCOA**, only in this specific exercise, **ResidualCapacity** will be 0 because it was assumed that in this ideal region there were no existing coal power plants installed before 2015.

Tip: this is not true for **PWROHC** (Oil power plant technology that we will add next), be sure to add Residual Capacity for this technology in your model!

Repeat the same steps for:

- 1) **PWROHC** - Light Fuel Oil Power Plant
- 2) **PWRNGS001** - Gas Power Plant (CCGT)
- 3) **PWRNGS002** - Gas Power Plant (SCGT)

using the data provided in the [DataPrep file](#).

You have now added 4 thermal power plants (**PWRCOA**, **PWROHC**, **PWRNGS001**, **PWRNGS002**) and 1 fuel (**ELC001**) to your model.

Define the existing transmission network

We will repeat the exercise once more giving the example of a technology which represents the **transmission network (PWRTRN)**. When representing the transmission technology, the following parameters must be considered:

- **InputActivityRatio:** defines the rate of fuel consumed (i.e. Electricity from power plants)
- **OutputActivityRatio:** defines the fuel provided (i.e. Electricity)
- **CapacityToActivityUnit:** It is used to convert data related to the Capacity of technology into the Activity it can generate. For primary supply technology, this value should be set to 1.
- **Fixed Cost:** defines the fixed Operation & Maintenance cost (\$/kW)
- **CapitalCost:** defines the overnight investment cost of the plant (\$/kW)
- **OperationalLife:** defines the lifetime of the technology (in years)
- **ResidualCapacity:** defines the existing capacity of the technology (in GW) and its expected decommissioning

Let's add **PWRTRN** - the technology representing the transmission grid

1. Go to SETS and in cell B14 change the name from "TEC00" to "**PWRTRN**" and the description to "**Electricity Transmission**". In this way, we add the technology that will be transmitting Electricity from Power Plants (**ELC001**) into a fictitious fuel that is the Electricity After Transmission (**ELC002**). This is done to account for the transmission grid losses.
2. Now let's add the **Electricity after transmission (ELC002)** in Cell E8 following the same procedure.
3. Next, go to Parameters Sheet and filter out in Column C for **PWRTRN** (as done previously).
4. Add the data for **PWRTRN** as for the tables below and as given in the [DataPrep file](#).
 - a. **InputActivityRatio**: choose the ELC001 row (Cell K21567) and add data from 2015 to 2070

21563	InputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	ELC003	0	0	0	0
21564	InputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	COA	0	0	0	0
21565	InputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	OIL	0	0	0	0
21566	InputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	NGS	0	0	0	0
21567	InputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	ELC001	1.05	1.05	1.05	1.05
21568	InputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	ELC002	0	0	0	0
21569	InputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	COM007	0	0	0	0
21570	InputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	COM008	0	0	0	0

b. OutputActivityRatio:

31724	OutputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	NGS	0	0	0	0
31725	OutputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	ELC001	0	0	0	0
31726	OutputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	ELC002	1	1	1	1
31727	OutputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	COM007	0	0	0	0
31728	OutputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	COM008	0	0	0	0
31729	OutputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	COM009	0	0	0	0

- c. **CapacityToActivityUnit, CapitalCost and FixedCost** respectively in rows 19572, 19771 and 20972. Fixed cost for transmission tech will be 0.

19373	CapacityOfOneTechnologyUnit	PWRTRN		0	0	0	0
19572	CapacityToActivityUnit	PWRTRN		31.356			
19771	CapitalCost	PWRTRN		365	365	365	365
20004	EmissionActivityRatio	PWRTRN	EMIC02	0	0	0	0
20005	EmissionActivityRatio	PWRTRN	EMICH4	0	0	0	0
20006	EmissionActivityRatio	PWRTRN	EMIFGA	0	0	0	0
20007	EmissionActivityRatio	PWRTRN	EMIN2O	0	0	0	0
20008	EmissionActivityRatio	PWRTRN	EMIREN	0	0	0	0
20972	FixedCost	PWRTRN		0	0	0	0

d. OperationalLife

21611	InputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	COM049	0	0	0	0
21612	InputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	COM050	0	0	0	0
31131	OperationalLife	PWRTRN		50			
31722	OutputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	ELC003	0	0	0	0
31723	OutputActivityRatio	PWRTRN	COA	0	0	0	0

- e. **ResidualCapacity**: defines the existing capacity of the technology (in GW) and its expected decommissioning.

Define the existing distribution network

We will repeat the exercise once more giving the example of a technology which represents the **distribution network (PWRDIST)**. (Very similar to **PWRTRN**)

Try it: Let's add **PWRDIST** - the technology representing the distribution network

1. Go to SETS and in cell B15 change the name from "TEC009" to "**PWRDIST**" and the description to "**Electricity distribution**". In this way, we added the technology which will convert the Electricity After Transmission (**ELC002**) into Electricity after distribution (**ELC003**).
2. We don't need to add **Electricity after Distribution as we had that already defined in Cell E1**.
3. Next, go to Parameters Sheet and filter out in Column C for **PWRDIST** (as done previously).
4. Add the data for **PWRDIST** as for the tables below and as given in the [DataPrep file](#).
 - a. **InputActivityRatio**: choose the Electricity After transmission row (Cell K21618) and add data from 2015 to 2070

InputActivityRatio	PWRDIST	COM007	COM008	COM009	COM010
21615	PWRDIST	OIL	0	0	0
21616	PWRDIST	NGS	0	0	0
21617	PWRDIST	ELC001	0	0	0
21618	PWRDIST	ELC002	1.17	1.16733	1.16467
21619	PWRDIST	COM007	0	0	0
21620	PWRDIST	COM008	0	0	0
21621	PWRDIST	COM009	0	0	0

b. **OutputActivityRatio**:

OutputActivityRatio	PWRDIST	ELC003	COA	OIL	NGS
21662	PWRDIST	COM050	0	0	0
31132	PWRDIST		1		
31772	PWRDIST	ELC003	1	1	1
31773	PWRDIST	COA	0	0	0
31774	PWRDIST	OIL	0	0	0
31775	PWRDIST	NGS	0	0	0

- c. **CapacityToActivityUnit, CapitalCost and FixedCost** respectively in rows 19573, 19772 and 20973. Fixed costs will be zero.

1220	CapacityFactor	PwRDIST				1	1	1	1
19374	CapacityOfOneTechnologyUnit	PwRDIST				0	0	0	0
19573	CapacityToActivityUnit	PwRDIST			31.536				
19772	CapitalCost	PwRDIST				2502	2502	2502	2502
20009	EmissionActivityRatio	PwRDIST	EMIC02			0	0	0	0
20010	EmissionActivityRatio	PwRDIST	EMICH4			0	0	0	0
20011	EmissionActivityRatio	PwRDIST	EMIFGA			0	0	0	0
20012	EmissionActivityRatio	PwRDIST	EMIN2O			0	0	0	0
20013	EmissionActivityRatio	PwRDIST	EMIREN			0	0	0	0
20973	FixedCost	PwRDIST				0	0	0	0

d. OperationalLife

21661	InputActivityRatio	PwRDIST	COM049						0
21662	InputActivityRatio	PwRDIST	COM050						0
31132	OperationalLife	PwRDIST					70		
31772	OutputActivityRatio	PwRDIST	ELC003						1
31773	OutputActivityRatio	PwRDIST	COA						0
31774	OutputActivityRatio	PwRDIST	OIL						0

- e. **ResidualCapacity**: defines the existing capacity of the technology (in GW) and its expected decommissioning

Run the model and check results on production by technology and capacity of each technology

This is the graph showing the Annual Electricity Production (PJ) results for this exercise. You should obtain this from the Results_Visualization_Template.xlsx file after running the model and following the steps explained in **Hands-on 3**.

Remember to filter for **PWROHC**, **PWRNGS002**, **PWRNGS001**, and **PWRCOA** to visualize the results from this exercise.

